

FACTOR OF RESPONSIBILITY AND DUTY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

Mamatqobilov Tursunmurad Doniyorovich

Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Associate Professor of the Department of Humanities of the Academy,

candidate of political sciences

Colonel A.V. Khusenov

Annotation - The article emphasizes the importance of the role of peace and stability in the organization of social and spiritual and educational work, as well as the importance of living and working with a sense of belonging to every citizen of the country.

Keywords: spiritual and educational work, the activities of leading personnel, social and cultural life, patriotism.

INTRODUCTION

Social-political, spiritual-educational and trade-economic issues are gaining importance in the context of large-scale reforms implemented in new Uzbekistan. That's why President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, relying on the principles of peace, stability and humanity, puts the life, dreams, pains and dreams of every person living in our country in the center of our attention and increasing the efficiency of tasks in this regard as the most important issue on the agenda. From the point of view of social policy, the issues of creating local jobs, opening wide opportunities for the development of entrepreneurship and private property, caring for youth, women, the elderly and disabled, and paying attention to needy people are reflected in the adopted state programs. The idea of "Let's live freely and prosperously in the new Uzbekistan" adopted on the occasion of the 29th anniversary of independence is

based on great historical experiences. Also, in accordance with our future plans, Uzbekistan is boldly advancing from national recovery to national growth.

Resolution PQ-3898 of August 4, 2018 of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising the moral and educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and moral and educational activities in the Armed Forces system introduced on this basis in accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of "Holy Motherland, it is an honorable duty to protect it!" idea was put forward. Also, in the Armed Forces system, every Friday of the week is designated as the "Day of Moral Elevation and Patriotism", and it is necessary to encourage the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The goal is to protect the sovereignty of our country, territorial integrity, and the peace of our people with loyalty, which is recognized as the highest task.

WIDE-SCALE REFORMS

Wide-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, to ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, to develop our country in all respects, and to raise its prestige in the international arena.

We are sure that under the leadership of our President, all attention is focused on the development of the society in the policy of Uzbekistan, which is on the path of developing a legal democratic state and a fair civil society based on a free market economy. The activities of public organizations, political institutions and mass media are synchronized with today's processes in the implementation of comprehensive reforms aimed at the liberalization of state administration, improvement of the state and society. The fact that the state and its policies are focused only on the benefit of the people, on ensuring the peace and stable life of the country's citizens is reflected in the adopted laws, decrees and decisions of the President and is implemented in life. Along with determining the material and cultural appearance of the society, this has a positive effect on the spiritual and

educational, moral thinking and outlook of the country's citizens, and on their spiritual experiences. That is why it creates an opportunity to harmonize the relations between the state and the citizens, the authorities and the population based on justice. Under the leadership of our head of state, our people live peacefully, positive economic changes are taking place step by step in our country. New opportunities are opening for enterprising, knowledgeable, hardworking people.

The principle that the people should serve our people and not the state agencies is being widely applied in life. Life itself shows the necessity of achieving justice in the legal system, ensuring citizens' confidence in the future, and raising the human factor by making an impartial assessment of the activities of state bodies. Ensuring the viability and enforcement of adopted laws should become a priority in society. Now, in the state and non-state sector, as well as in the entire production, there is a need for specialist employees, employees who quickly get involved in economic reforms, and personnel who meet the requirements of market relations and the requirements of modern world technology. Therefore, it is an important task to move from general production to production based on advanced technologies, to increase the volume of export of products, and to train employees who think in a new way in today's market conditions.

The fact that, on the initiative of the President, every Thursday of the week has been announced as Crime Prevention Day, mobile court hearings are being held, and the system of opening and effective communication with the people is being established, which is evidence of the practical manifestation of democratic principles.

Deepening and expanding the scope of structural reforms, modernizing the economy, ensuring stable and balanced macroeconomic indicators, making investments, developing free economic zones, strengthening the private ownership sector and further improving the favorable environment for business, employment of the population as an important condition for the population's income and standard of living. The large-scale reforms implemented by the head of our state in terms of

ensuring employment and promoting exports in all respects are recognized as an important factor determining the development of our country.

Now, the members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and the deputies of the Legislative Chamber meet with their constituents on the last ten days of every month and develop measures to legally solve the problems that are bothering the population, and the fact that the authorities are not indifferent to the appeals of the citizens creates the basis for people to live with a sense of belonging to the changes taking place in society. . At the moment, the consistent continuation of a well-thought-out tight monetary policy is seen as an important issue for job creation.

Today's world is experiencing an information onslaught. For this reason, information acquisition is becoming one of the most urgent issues in the population's thinking. Now, while analyzing the interest, mood, and social status of all individuals and social groups, providing jobs to the unemployed remains an important issue. Development of non-state sector is also one of the most important effective means. Because the non-state sector is considered as the starting link in the formation of civil society. In these processes, man appears as a subject of society in solving his social problems. We have to admit that due to our carelessness, indifference and some shortcomings in our work, some young people have fallen under the influence of criminal groups, extremists and alien, destructive ideas.

Great creative works are being carried out throughout our country. The appearance of our Shahapy villages is becoming more beautiful day by day, affordable housing and infrastructure networks are being built for the population based on exemplary projects. Renewable electricity, clean drinking water and natural gas supplies are improving. Don't you think that the abundance of goods in the shops in the bazaars, and the abundance of our tables? All this, first of all, is due to our independence, and moreover, the peace and tranquility prevailing in our country. It motivates all of us to sacrifice.

Ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country was considered a priority of our state policy. Representatives of more than 130

nationalities and peoples living in our country have united in 138 national-cultural centers and live peacefully as children of a big family under the slogan "Uzbekistan is our common home". At the root of this is a great humanitarian policy. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2017, the Committee on International Relations and Friendly Relations with Foreign Countries was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. The main goal of this is to consistently continue the state policy aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in our society.

We must always be alert and vigilant in the present time, when the process of globalization has intensified in the world, competition and mutual contradictions are increasing on a global scale, threats such as radicalism, terrorism, extremism, proselytism and "mass culture" are expanding. Life itself requires us to further increase our mobilization through the ideas of "Protect your own home", "Protect your own child". Ensuring the integrity of the country's borders, strengthening the combat potential of our Armed Forces, we need to educate our young men and women in the spirit of patriotism.

Today there are about two billion young people in the world, and the issues of studying, analyzing and finding solutions to the problems of most of them remain relevant.

Famous sociologist - futurologist E. Toffler, - A new person is not being formed, a new social character is being formed. That is why it is necessary to define the characteristic features of the character, not the figure of a person, because it can be evaluated by tomorrow's development.

On September 19, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly took into account the proposal to develop special resolutions on enlightenment and religious tolerance and youth issues, and on December 12, 2018, at the next session of the UN General Assembly - it is worth noting that a special resolution on enlightenment and religious tolerance was adopted.

In order to encourage the level of education of the youth of Uzbekistan and the implementation of their advanced ideas, from September 14, 2016 - to ensure the implementation of the law on state policy regarding youth and from the Decree of the head of our country dated July 5, 2017 - to improve the effectiveness of state policy regarding youth and to support the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan As a result, in the development of the new Uzbekistan, attention to youth is being strengthened. For example, the Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established in accordance with the Decree of the President of June 30, 2020 "On the measures to fundamentally reform the state policy regarding youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan and take it to a new level". The goal is to strengthen their participation in the activities of the state and our society by studying and analyzing youth problems, selecting and guiding young people. Also, in order to ensure the implementation of paragraph 21 of the State Program approved by the decree of the President of March 2, 2020, it was envisaged to establish the procedure for the formation of youth parliaments and their composition in the presence of both chambers of the Youth Parliament. Based on this, in accordance with the extensive discussion and the experience of foreign countries, on June 29, 2020, the Legislative Chamber of the Youth Parliament of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Youth Union of Uzbekistan signed an agreement on the establishment of the Youth Parliament in the presence of the Legislative Chamber. With this agreement, the Youth Parliament, Republican Commission, Charter, Regulations and organizational structure were approved.

Human thinking creates different thoughts, views, ideas and teachings during the perception of reality. So, ideas are also a product of human thinking. But not every thought or view, judgment or point of view created by thought can be an idea, only the most powerful, influential, and powerful thoughts can be an idea. Therefore, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev, a video selector meeting on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational affairs and strengthening

the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard will be held on January 19, 2021. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values, he said. In fact, the rich heritage left by our ancestors, national values, moral norms, traditions, examples of folk oral creativity, ethnocultural features such as hard work, religious tolerance, generosity, philosophical observation, benevolence characteristic of our people will inevitably serve as a spiritual factor for the Third Renaissance. After all, these spiritual factors did not appear yesterday or today. These values have passed the test of centuries and have been cherished in the hearts of our people to this day, which helps in educating the next generation as worthy successors, raising the population, especially the youth, in the spirit of respect and tolerance towards the religion and philosophy of Islam and other religious denominations. , serves as an important moral basis for further strengthening the atmosphere of interethnic harmony and mutual kindness. It also ensures the priority of spiritual and moral criteria, national and universal values.

RESULTS

As a result of the wide-ranging reforms and creative works being implemented in our country, the way of thinking and worldview of our people is changing. This includes the implementation of the following tasks:

- turning a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement in society by widely promoting the idea of "From national revival to national rise" based on the principle of goodness and humanity; ensuring the integrity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods; organization of work in the direction of propaganda and education on a scientific basis, increasing the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in the field, introducing a permanent monitoring system aimed at strengthening the stability of the social and moral environment; implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at eliminating vices such as indifference to the fate of the country, localism, nepotism, corruption, disrespect for family values and irresponsibility in the

education of young people, etc. is intended, and instead of CONCLUSION, the following points can be expressed:

1. The legal foundations of the foundation of the Third Renaissance period were created in the new Uzbekistan, including the laws on the development of various fields adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan, presidential decrees and decisions, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as orders and decisions announced and implemented by relevant ministries and committees. is the institutional basis.

2. The Renaissance process took place twice in the territory of Central Asia, and in this process it is observed that not only scientists and thinkers who made an incomparable contribution to the development of science appeared, but also new sciences were created and developed in this region. According to the genetic theory, if there were geniuses in the past, this process will be repeated in the next generations. Therefore, if sufficient conditions are created for the development of science and attention is paid, this process can certainly happen again. After all, "a flowing river will not stop flowing."

3. Strong spirituality based on the rich spiritual heritage and national values left by our ancestors, ethnic and national values, moral norms, customs, examples of folk oral creativity, ethno-cultural characteristics such as hard work, religious tolerance, generosity, philosophical observation, benevolence typical of our people. Serves as a spiritual factor for the Renaissance. After all, these spiritual factors did not appear yesterday or today. These have passed the test of centuries and have been cherished in the hearts of our people until today, which is considered a priceless treasure for educating the future generation as a worthy successor.

The main goal of the Youth Parliament is to provide comprehensive support to the youth of the country, increase their legal awareness and culture, turn them into an active social stratum of society, enrich their political knowledge and skills in practice, involve young people in the process of legislation and law-making, and ensure wide promotion of adopted laws among young people. to increase their

involvement in the life of the parliament. Also, developing proposals for improving legal documents related to the protection of the rights, freedoms and interests of young people, discussing current problems of law-making and law enforcement practice with the participation of young people and preparing proposals aimed at eliminating them, applying the rules of legal and technical formalization of legal drafts into practice a testament to the focus on youth.

Now, through this parliament, our youth will participate in the meetings of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their council, committees and commissions, associations of deputies, and will be able to exchange experience and information with relevant international and foreign organizations in the prescribed manner.

Citizens of Uzbekistan aged 18-30 are elected to the Youth Parliament for a two-year term (except for those who are incompetent and detained in penal institutions). Regional commissions will be established to elect members to the Youth Parliament. The commission organizes election processes in two stages. At the first stage, candidates participate in the district (city) commission with their pre-election program. At the end of the first stage, the commission will elect five candidates, that is, one candidate from each political party, by secret ballot. In the second stage, candidates will participate in the Council of People's Deputies of the relevant district (city) with the presentation of the pre-election program. People's deputies of the respective district (city) elect one candidate by secret ballot. Therefore, the youth parliament is accountable to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, relevant political parties and the Youth Union of Uzbekistan in its activities. The main task envisaged is to strengthen the life experience of young people, who are considered the social layer of society.

After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, our main goal will be to create all opportunities for our children to fully realize their talents and abilities, their noble aspirations, increase their social activity, and take a worthy place in life.

In fact, in the implementation of important state programs on health care, environmental protection, providing jobs to the population, especially young people, supporting the groups in need of social protection, and other issues of great social importance, the state itself is the guiding force. determined the strategy.

Also, during today's pandemic, the fact that our state is at the center of social and political affairs, and the organization of generosity and support measures by selfless people of our people as a partner, shows humanitarian feelings in the principle of the reforms being carried out in our country.

As a result of large-scale reforms in the Armed Forces system, we are always proud to show the bravery of our national heroes such as Shiroq, Tomaris, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Amir Temur, Babur as an example to our military personnel. Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure. The mobility of structures, combat capability, and physical and moral training of the military have increased. Units and units are equipped with modern weapons and combat equipment. The high fighting ability of the Armed Forces is the most important principle of the cohesion of the people of Uzbekistan and the education of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism through the development of economic, political, strategic and military-technical and scientific power. Therefore, due to the large-scale work in the military field, strict discipline and spiritual-enlightenment thinking will rise.

It is known that one of the goals and objectives of the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to stimulate scientific research and innovation activities in the direction of "Development of the field of education and science", to create effective mechanisms for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements, specialized in higher educational institutions and scientific research institutes special attention is paid to the organization of scientific experimental laboratories, high technology centers and technological parks.

Fundamental reforms and updates in the fields of science, education and innovation in our country require a deep study of the history of national military art,

the rich historical heritage of the Uzbek people, thereby developing the system of military science. On January 12 of this year, at the extended meeting of the Security Council, chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the head of state gave a number of important tasks for the development of the Armed Forces and further strengthening of the country's defense capabilities. In particular, regarding the training of military personnel and the development of military science, the President of the Republic of Armenia set the task of further improving the methods and methods of military training by deeply studying the history of national military art and modern combat practices.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that each of us should contribute to the large-scale reforms being implemented in our country under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Because the combination of high civic responsibility with a sense of belonging to the society serves the realization of our great goals.

In short, the development of the Motherland and the well-being of our people are based on the rise of the social-political, spiritual-educational, legal-cultural level of young people who are among the creators of New Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Part of the introduction. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2016.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility - should be the daily rule of every leader's activity". T.: Uzbekistan. 2017 year.
3. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. New Uzbekistan newspaper. January 25, 2020.
4. Khusenov A. et al. KEY TRENDS IN SUPPLY PEACE AND RESTORATION //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B10. – C. 226-229.
5. Mamatqabilov T. D. et al. SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL FOUNDATIONS OF

PATRIOTISM IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN //Science and Innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 53-60.

6. Sayfullayeva D. THE ROLE OF MONOLOGUE AND DIALOGUE IN KHUDOYBERDI TOKHTABAEV'S NOVEL" MUNGLI KOZLAR" //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. C10. – С. 154-158.

7. Mamatqabilov T., Sayfullayeva D., Abdukadirova R. PATRIOTISM OF MILITARY SERVANTS AND ITS SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL BASES //Science and innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. B2. – С. 128-132.

8. Mamatqabilov T., Yuldashev O., Eshmuradov D. IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY EDUCATION ISSUES OF GENDER QUALITY //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. B9. – С. 151-155.

9. Ашурбеков Р. Х., Эшмурадов Д. Э., Элмурадов Т. Д. ЦЕННОСТИ УЗБЕКОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И ШИРОКО ИЗВЕСТНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ КУЛЬТУР: СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ //Г–75 Гражданская авиация: прошлое, настоящее и будущее. – 2015. – С. 164.

10. Karimov I.A. Our way is to deepen the democratic reforms and continue the modernization process consistently. Volume 20. - Т.: Uzbekistan, 2012.

11. Abu Nasr Farabi. City of virtuous people. - Т.: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" state scientific publishing house. 2004.